

General Summary

Our research explored how artificial neural networks handle multiple tasks simultaneously. We focused on a recurrent neural network (RNN) trained to perform various tasks.

A recent study showed that this RNN displayed shared patterns, or "motifs," when performing different tasks with similar task periods. We investigated whether these shared patterns also meant the network used similar underlying processes, or "dynamics," for these task periods. We wanted to see if, beyond the shape of the motifs, the dynamics of similar task periods were also similar.

To investigate, we used a new tool called Dynamical Similarity Analysis (DSA), which compares the inner workings of different systems. We applied DSA to examine the RNN's activity during various tasks.

By combining shared patterns in multi-tasking networks with DSA, we aimed to gain insights into how artificial neural networks organize and process information when juggling multiple tasks.